

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Reflection of the Female Image in English Paremiology: A GenderBased Analysis

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Abstract

This article focuses on the formation of the female image in English proverbs and the manifestation of gender stereotypes within the paremiological worldview. The relevance of the study lies in its proposal to model gender identification in order to analyze stereotypical perceptions of women within the framework of the English paremiological system. The research identifies how the image of femininity is expressed through linguistic means and highlights its national and cultural specificities. The results show that the female image in English proverbs is portrayed in a contradictory manner, combining both positive and negative traits. The analysis reveals that negative ethnotypical characteristics prevail in these proverbs, indicating a high degree of androcentrism in English paremiological units. Furthermore, the female image is interpreted from an instrumental perspective—evaluated in terms of its usefulness to men.

Keywords: gender stereotype, paremiological worldview, female image, English proverbs, linguacultural, communicative-pragmatic approach, proverb semantics.

Introduction

In recent years, scholarly interest in the issue of gender stereotypes has been increasing, especially within linguistics and the analysis of proverbs. «Proverbs are stable expressions that emerge as the product of folk wisdom and serve to model human behavior» Абакумова О. Б., Кирюхина Н. В. (2021). «Proverbs, sayings, riddles, and other paremiological units form the cultural layer of language and are a significant reflection of societal experience» Аносов Е. А.(2012). Such units serve as valuable sources for identifying gender stereotypes and representations. They convey generalized perceptions, emotional-expressive evaluations of men and women existing in society. Gender stereotypes are generalized conceptions Regarding male and female behavior formed within a specific cultural framework .Brown H. D.(1994)

The expression of national mentality and stereotypes through folk proverbs has been studied by numerous scholars Butler J, (1990) ; Садохин А. П.(2005); Словарь гендерных терминов(2002), and others. As noted by Connell R. W.(1993)., proverbs are a core reflection of human experience and express the values present in society.

Research Objectives

The main tasks of this study are as follows:

To identify the manifestations of gender stereotypes in English proverbs;

To define criteria for the identification of femininity;

To observe the influence of gender stereotypes within the paremiological Worldview;

To analyze the linguistic representation of the female image;

To determine the national and cultural specificities of femininity.

Literature Review

Gender is a model that defines the social roles and status of men and women in

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Society, forming as a cognitive unit in human thinking Brown H. D.(1994). The Research relies on the model for analyzing femininity and masculinity developed by Crystal D.(1997). And Городникова М. Д.(2002). As its methodological Foundation.

The following sources were chosen as research material:

Archer T. (1962) The Proverb and An Index to the Proverb Bertram A. (1993) NTC's Dictionary of Proverbs and Clichés. Lincolnwood: NTC Publishing Group

Bryan G. B., Mieder W. (2005) Anglo-American Proverbs and Proverbial Phrases Found in Literary Sources of the 19th and 20th Centuries

Speake J. The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs, 5th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press Inc. (2008)

Stevenson B. The Home Book of Proverbs, Maxims and Familiar Phrases. NY: The Macmillan (1956)

Methods

Structural-semantic analysis

Descriptive-classificatory methods

Linguocultural analysis

Statistical analysis

Analysis and Results

Three main criteria were considered in describing the female image:

Physical Characteristics – appearance, age, physiological features.

Proverbs in this group (23%) focus on evaluating beauty. For example:

«There was never a mirror that told a woman she was ugly»

«A woman's hair is her crowning glory»

While a woman's age is often judged by her appearance, a man's is linked to his inner state.

For instance:

«A man is as old as he feels, and a woman as old as she looks»

English proverbs emphasize that suffering and an unhealthy lifestyle prematurely age women:

«Sorrow and evil life make soon an old wife»

Psychological Characteristics – intellectual, emotional, and behavioral traits.

This group comprises 32% of the proverbs and often carries a negative Connotation. For example:

«A woman's advice is no great thing, but he who would take it is a fool»

«Women in state affairs are like monkeys in glass-shops»

«A woman's hair is long, her tongue is longer»

English proverbs stress women's emotional volatility and mood swings:

«A woman's mind and wind change often»

«Winter weather and women's thoughts change often»

«A woman laughs when she can but cries whenever she wishes»

«Female is one head with two faces»

Socio-Ethnic Characteristics – social role, family status, societal position.

This group represents 45% of the proverbs, where women are portrayed as wives, mothers, homemakers, or daughters-in-law:

«A man without a wife is but half a man»

«A man's best fortune, or his worst, is his wife»

«A worthy woman is the crown of her husband»

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«A good wife lost is God's gift lost»

The importance of a woman's loyalty is also emphasized:

«A true wife is her husband's better half»

«A faithless wife is the shipwreck of the home»

Additionally, women's industriousness and domestic workload are highlighted:

«A woman's work is never done»

Conclusion

The representation of the female image in the English paremiological system shows how deeply gender stereotypes are embedded in societal thought. The analysis demonstrates that the female image in English proverbs is portrayed in a contradictory manner—associated with both positive (diligence, loyalty, beauty) and negative (emotional instability, intellectual weakness, talkativeness, volatility) attributes.

Evaluations based on age, appearance, emotional state, and social role reflect established gender stereotypes. Furthermore, the female image is often assessed from a male, instrumentalist perspective—based on usefulness. This highlights the Dominance of an androcentric worldview in English paremiological expressions. The results of the study confirm that proverbs are not only linguistic but also cultural, social, and historical tools that reinforce gender stereotypes.

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